

Performance and Energy Analysis of Hydraulic Regenerative Energy Systems in Heavy Duty Lifting Machine

Labanyo Bacher

College of Safety and Resources Engineering, Central South University, China

Protiva Sarkar

Chemistry Department of Govt B.L.College, Khulna, Bangladesh

Hasan Md Mehedy

College of Mechanical Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology, China

Article History:

Received: 06.12.2025 Revised: 27.12.2025 Accepted: 28.12.2025 Published: 30.12.2025

ABSTRACT:

Modern industry faces the crucial problem of energy conservation for industrial vehicles. Energy conservation based on the potential energy of forklift trucks is one of the effective measures for solving the problem. However, the idea for solving the problem is based on the use of the hydraulic motor's flow rate for the flow rate from the cylinder during the process of lifting heavy loads and lowering the forks. To achieve energy conservation, the torque speed of the generator must be optimized based on the speed of the lowered forks. To achieve the goal, the system for the optimized energy saving efficiency by controlling the angle of the variable hydraulic motor's swashplate by means of the GA (Genetic Algorithm) was proposed. To verify the results obtained from the proposed system, the fixed motor model system and the variable motor system by means of the AMESim software simulation was used. According to the research data obtained from the simulation process, the proposed system's optimized swashplate angle improved the energy-saving efficiency by 6-8%

Keywords: Heavy duty Forklift, Energy Regeneration, Hydraulic Energy, Variable Speed Motor, System Efficiency.

Suggested Citation: L. Bacher, P. Sarkar, H.M. Mehedy, "Performance and Energy Analysis of Hydraulic Regenerative Energy Systems in Heavy Duty Lifting Machine," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 4(1), pp. 100-109, Jan-Feb 2026. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2026.4(1).05

INTRODUCTION

With recent international environmental pollution issues emerging, the construction equipment sector is demanding technological development to reduce exhaust gas emissions and energy consumption. [1] Therefore, energy regeneration systems are attracting attention as a solution to these environmental pollution and energy consumption issues. Energy regeneration systems, such as boom regeneration for construction equipment (excavators) and descent regeneration for industrial elevators, are currently being studied extensively in various fields. [2,3,4,5] However, research on energy regeneration in forklifts, such as industrial vehicles, is limited. Currently, considerable research is being conducted on various energy regeneration systems and strategies used in

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

excavators. [6,7,8,9,10] Typical energy regeneration methods include directly storing the hydraulic energy generated by the cylinder's lowering using an accumulator, and storing it as electrical energy in batteries and supercapacitors using a generator. However, forklifts, which use hydraulic energy to lift objects, like excavators, there has been little research on energy recovery. Driving and lifting account for the largest portion of forklift operations. Forklifts consume energy when lifting cargo, raising the lift cylinder, and lowering it using the fork and load weight. Furthermore, to ensure safety during lowering operations, a flow control valve is used to regulate the flow rate into the tank, controlling the lowering speed. The hydraulic energy flowing into the tank is wasted, so the core of this research is to recover it into electrical energy using a hydraulic motor and generator. In a previous study on forklift energy recovery, [11] proposed an energy recovery system for forklifts using an integrated motor/generator model. However, due to the use of a fixed motor, the system failed to operate at the optimal efficiency point for both the motor and generator. Furthermore, [12] used a variable hydraulic motor, but because it used a rule-based control strategy to control the swash plate angle of the hydraulic motor, it failed to operate the system at the optimal efficiency point for each operating condition. Furthermore, the control conditions and parameters used in the control strategy were determined through trial and error based on the experimenter's experience, making it difficult to say that it maximized the efficiency of the overall system. This study applied an energy regeneration system using a variable hydraulic motor to the hydraulic system of a conventional forklift. This study aimed to increase overall energy efficiency by controlling the swash plate angle of the hydraulic motor, considering efficiency according to the workload and lowering speed. System optimization requires consideration of the volumetric and mechanical efficiencies of the hydraulic motor, as well as the efficiency of the generator. However, these factors exhibit nonlinear behavior within the system, making optimization difficult. This issue is addressed through GA. Using AMESim, a hydraulic analysis software, we built a simulation model and compared its efficiency with that of a conventional system using a fixed hydraulic motor. We also optimized the swash plate angle of the hydraulic motor using a GA in Matlab/Simulink, considering the lift's descent speed.

FORKLIFT LIFT RECOVERY SYSTEM

The system proposed in this study to improve energy recovery efficiency is shown in [Figure. 1](#). The main components of the system are as follows: 1. Electric motor, 2. Main hydraulic pump, 3. Relief valve, 4. Main control valve for MCV lift, 5. Hydraulic motor, 6. Generator, 7. Flow control valve, and 8. Lift cylinder.

Figure 1. The Proposed Forklift System

Figure. 2 is a flow chart of the proposed system, and the control strategy depicted therein is as follows. When the cylinder rises based on the joystick angle, the main control valve is activated. As the electric motor rotates, the working fluid discharged from the main hydraulic pump passes through the regulated main control valve and flows into the cylinder, raising the cylinder. The opening area of the main control valve is proportional to the joystick angle (α). When $\alpha > 0$, the cylinder rises, and when $\alpha < 0$, the cylinder descends. The ascending and descending speeds are determined by the size of α .

Figure 2. Flow Chart of the Control Strategy

When the cylinder is lowered, the operating fluid discharged from the cylinder is adjusted by adjusting the opening area of the flow control valve, thereby controlling the lowering speed of the lift. Instead of sending the fluid discharged from the cylinder directly to the tank, the hydraulic energy is converted into electrical energy via a hydraulic motor.

During forklift operation, when the lift is raised, the lift and the object it lifts possess high potential energy due to their weight. This potential energy is converted into hydraulic energy discharged from the cylinder when the lift is lowered. Instead of sending this energy directly to the hydraulic tank, the opening area of the flow control valve is adjusted to generate high pressure within the chamber. At this time, the working fluid is passed through the hydraulic motor, which rotates the connected generator and generates electrical energy. The most significant factors influencing this electrical energy generation are the load and the lowering speed. Depending on the load and lowering speed, the pressure and flow rate of the fluid entering the hydraulic motor vary. By appropriately adjusting the swash plate angle of the hydraulic motor and the suction flow rate, the efficiency of the entire system can be increased.

SIMULATION

Figure 3 shows the lift energy regeneration system described above, modeled using AMESim. Table 1 and Table 2 show the parameters applied to the AMESim model and the simulation conditions used to demonstrate the shift in efficiency point. When building the simulation model, the forklift's durability test and the allowable load and operating speed during actual operations were considered. Two load conditions were selected: 2,000 kg, the load required for vehicle durability testing, and 1,500 kg, the typical allowable load. Two speeds were selected: 0.1 and 0.15 m/s, which are typically applied under the previously selected load conditions.

A system was built to measure the power used by the hydraulic pump and the power generated by the hydraulic motor under each condition. The efficiency was then compared between the existing system using a fixed motor and the proposed system using a variable motor.

Figure 3. Forklift Energy Regeneration Model Using AMESim

Table 1. Parameter of Hydraulic Circuit

Component	Value	Remark and Unit
Hydraulic Pump	20	Displacement of gear pump [cc/rev]
Hydraulic Motor	20	Displacement of hydraulic motor [cc/rev]
Hydraulic Cylinder	42	Piston dia [mm]
	36	Rod dia [mm]
	1.5	Stroke length [m]

Table 2. Simulation Condition by Mass & Lifting Velocity

Case	Mass[kg]	Lifting Velocity[m/s]
Case1	2000	0.1
Case2	2000	0.15
Case3	1500	0.1
Case4	1500	0.15

RESULTS AND OPTIMIZATION

Simulation Results

Figure 4 shows the generator efficiency map, applying four conditions to the existing and proposed circuits. This shows that using a variable motor to control the flow rate yields a higher efficiency (η_{gn}) than using a fixed motor.

Figure 5 to Figure 8 show the torque and rotational speed output from the hydraulic motor according to the swash plate angle and lowering speed for loads of 2,000 kg and 1,500 kg, respectively. The hydraulic motor rotational speed increases as the swash plate angle decreases and the lowering speed increases. The torque also increases as the lowering speed decreases and the swash plate angle increases. Here, the hydraulic motor torque includes the generator load torque.

Consequently, as the swash plate angle of the hydraulic motor changes, the output torque and rotational speed change, which in turn affects the generator efficiency (η_{gn}).

Furthermore, using the efficiency maps shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10, the total efficiency and volumetric efficiency are calculated according to the hydraulic motor pressure and discharge rate. Using equation (1), the mechanical efficiency of the hydraulic motor is calculated. Based on the

volumetric efficiency and mechanical efficiency of the hydraulic motor, equations (2) and equation (3) are used to determine the actual motor output torque and rotational speed. This allows for the calculation of power generation considering the full efficiencies of the generator and hydraulic motor.

Figure 4. Generator Efficiency Map for Each Case

$$\eta_m = \frac{\eta_o}{\eta_v} \quad (1)$$

$$T_m = \eta_m \cdot P \cdot D \quad (2)$$

$$\omega_m = \frac{\eta_v \cdot Q}{D} \quad (3)$$

$$E_{pump} = \omega_p T_p \quad (4)$$

$$E_{reg-th} = \omega_m T_m \quad (5)$$

Figure 5. Simulation Result of Rotational Speed at Load of 2000kg

Figure 6. Simulation Result of Torque at Load of 2000kg

$$E_{sys} = E_{pump} - E_{reg} \quad (7)$$

$$\eta_{save} = \frac{E_{pump} - E_{sys}}{E_{pump}} = \frac{E_{reg}}{E_{pump}} \quad (8)$$

Figure 11. Velocity of Lift Down

Figure 12. Result of GA Optimization

Figure 12. Result of GA Optimization

Another issue to consider after optimization is the issue of controlling the swash plate angle. Because the generator's efficiency map is not linear, the controlled swash plate angle also does not exhibit linear behavior. However, such rapid swash plate angle changes are detrimental to the controllability and durability of the hydraulic motor. Therefore, the swash plate angle change over time was compared with the swash plate angle at the immediately preceding sampling time and adjusted to minimize efficiency degradation. Figure 13 shows how the fluid output changes under given speed conditions according to the adjusted hydraulic motor swash plate angle.

Optimized displacement using optimized swash plate control, Full displacement, which behaves similarly to a fixed motor of the same capacity, and Half displacement, which delivers half the flow rate, were applied to 2,000 kg and 1,500 kg loads, respectively. The resulting power and power consumption are shown in from Figures 14 to Figure 17.

Figure 14. Generated Power at Case of 2000kg

Figure 15. Electrical Energy at Case of 2000kg

Figure 16. Generated Power at Case of 1500kg

Figure 17. Electrical Energy at Case of 1500kg

Table 3. Energy Saving Efficiency of Each Case

Mod	Mass[kg]	η_{save}	Improve[%]
Full	2000	0.2112	-
	1500	0.1820	-
Half	2000	0.1679	-
	1500	0.1383	-
Optimized	2000	0.2287	8.3165
	1500	0.1932	6.1121

To compare the overall energy-saving efficiency of the existing and proposed systems, E_{pump} , corresponding to the total input energy of the system, was calculated using equation (4). In each case, the energy obtained from the generator was calculated using equation (5). The inverter efficiency (η_{inv}) and battery efficiency (η_{bat}) were set to 0.9 and 0.85, respectively. These values were substituted into equation (7) and equation (8) to calculate the energy-saving efficiency, and the results are shown in Table 3. The optimized system shows efficiencies of 0.2287 and 0.1932 respectively, which are higher than the previous system.

CONCLUSION

In this study, a novel lift regeneration system utilizing a variable hydraulic motor was proposed to improve the efficiency of the existing forklift lift regeneration system using a fixed motor. The main results are as follows.

(1) A simulation model of the proposed system was built using AMESim. Using this model, torque and rotational speed were derived based on the efficiency map of the hydraulic motor and generator according to the workload and operating speed. The derived data was used to calculate the energy used and regenerated by the system.

(2) Considering the nonlinear efficiency characteristics of the hydraulic motor and generator, the swash angle of the hydraulic motor was optimized using a general-purpose algorithm (GA) to maximize energy efficiency. The optimized swash angle controlled the torque and rotational speed of the generator, maximizing power generation. Consequently, the proposed system increased energy efficiency by 8.31% for a 2,000 kg load and 6.11% for a 1,500 kg load. Based on this study, future research is planned on energy recovery in hybrid systems using variable hydraulic motors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to give a special thanks to Prof. Lei Ge for his guidance and numerous enlightening conversations throughout this research. Thank you to the staff of the Hydraulics Lab of Taiyuan University of Technology for their assistance in experiments, efficiency maps, as well as the machine worked.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this research, either financial or non-financial.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Yu and K. K. Ahn, "Energy regeneration and reuse of excavator swing system with hydraulic accumulator," *International Journal of Precision Engineering and Manufacturing-Green Technology*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–13, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s40684-019-00157-7.
- [2] Y. Yu, T. Do, Y. Park, and K. K. Ahn, "Energy saving of hybrid hydraulic excavator with innovative powertrain," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 2082, 2021, doi: 10.3390/app11052082.
- [3] T. C. Do, T. D. Dang, T. Dinh, and K. K. Ahn, "Developments in energy regeneration technologies for hydraulic excavators: A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 145, p. 111076, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2021.111076.
- [4] L. Li, T. Zhang, K. Wu, L. Lu, L. Lin, and H. Xu, "Design and research on electro-hydraulic drive and energy recovery system of the electric excavator boom," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 13, p. 4757, 2022, doi: 10.3390/en15134757.
- [5] T. C. Do, H. Truong, V. Dao, C. M. Ho, T. X. Dinh, T. D. Dang, and K. K. Ahn, "Energy management strategy of a PEM fuel cell excavator with a supercapacitor/battery hybrid power source," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 22, p. 4362, 2019, doi: 10.3390/en12224362.
- [6] T. Liang, L. Quan, L. Ge, L. Xia, and B. Wang, "Characteristics of a novel electrohydraulic multi-actuator system with low throttling losses and energy regeneration capability," *Chinese Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 38, art. no. 78, 2025, doi: 10.1186/s10033-025-01278-8.
- [7] G. Costa and N. Sepehri, "Hydraulic accumulators in energy efficient circuits," *Frontiers in Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 9, art. no. 1163293, 2023, doi: 10.3389/fmech.2023.1163293.
- [8] Y. Guo, X. Liao, H. Meng, F. Dong, and S. K. Yang, "Design, modeling, and simulation of a novel transducer for vibration energy recovery system of speed bump," *Transactions of the Canadian Society for Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 563–575, 2023, doi: 10.1139/tcsme-2022-0064.
- [9] Y. Chen, T. Zhang, H. Zhang, Z. Zhang, Q. Jia, H. Chen, H. Xu, and Y. Zhang, "Study on the effect of hydraulic energy storage on the performance of electro-mechanical-hydraulic power-

coupled electric vehicles,” *Electronics*, vol. 11, no. 20, p. 3344, 2022, doi: 10.3390/electronics11203344.

[10] M. Gao, L. Li, Q. Wang, and C. Liu, “Energy efficiency and dynamic analysis of a novel hydraulic system with double actuator,” *International Journal of Precision Engineering and Manufacturing-Green Technology*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 301–314, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s40684-019-00182-6.

[11] J. Cui, L. Quan, Z. Liu, Y. Hao, L. Ge, and W. Huang, “Design and control of a novel hybrid drive swing system for excavators integrating electrical and hydraulic energy recovery systems,” *Energy*, vol. 336, p. 138501, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2025.138501.

[12] Y. Yu, “Optimization of energy regeneration of hybrid hydraulic excavator boom system,” *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 244, p. 114447, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2021.114447.

